

Involving Children with Disabilities in Inclusive Education

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Abstract:

This article discusses the adaptation of children requiring special assistance to an inclusive educational environment. It highlights how inclusive education allows these children to communicate with others, grow to meet the demands of the social environment, and acquire life skills to manage their daily needs. It further emphasizes the creation of conditions in general education schools for them to study alongside their healthy peers under equal conditions, fostering friendships, learning lessons in a timely manner, and taking responsibility for completing assignments.

Keywords: Pedagogical, psychological, social environment, correction, abilities, skills, defect, communication, integration.

Currently, in the modern education system, the need to create a flexible learning environment that meets the needs of students and takes into account each individual's specific needs is increasing. International organizations such as the UN and UNESCO emphasize the implementation of inclusive education ideas, the creation of safe and comfortable learning environments for children and adults with special educational needs, and the promotion of social equality. One of the UN's educational policy directions is to ensure that inclusive education, which considers the diverse educational needs of children, is widely implemented by participant states.

UNESCO's programs, aimed at ensuring human rights and freedoms, focus on modernizing the norms, standards, and intellectual cooperation to ensure safe and accessible education for children and adults with special needs. These processes must be reflected across all levels of the education system, including among teachers and educational institutions. The openness and equality of education play a key role in expanding opportunities for each individual and ensuring social stability in society.

In our country, the legal norms for organizing inclusive education based on the integration of science, education, and production have been developed, taking into account the social needs and personal interests of students. Important tasks have been identified, such as strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, adapting curricula, improving access to quality health-supporting educational services, and training highly qualified personnel to facilitate inclusive education for children with special educational needs.

Several decrees and resolutions from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have laid the foundation for these developments. These include the following:

Decree PF-5270 (December 1, 2017) on "Measures for the radical improvement of the state support system for persons with disabilities,"

Decree PF-5712 (April 29, 2019) on the "Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030,"

Decree PF-6108 (November 6, 2020) on "Measures for the development of education, upbringing, and science in Uzbekistan's new development era,"

Decree PF-60 (January 28, 2022) on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026,"

Resolution PQ-4860 (October 13, 2020) on "Measures for further improving the educational system for children with special needs,"

Resolution 638 of the Cabinet of Ministers (October 12, 2021) on "Approval of regulatory legal documents regarding the education of children with special educational needs."

These documents outline key responsibilities, including modernizing educational content, providing methodological and didactic support for the process, and addressing personnel matters.

In Uzbekistan, significant work is being done to ensure the rights and freedoms of individuals with developmental disabilities, guarantee equal opportunities, remove barriers to daily activities, and organize and manage education with a modern approach. Efforts are also focused on enhancing the quality and effectiveness of education and ensuring continuity in education for all social groups in society.

The country is creating favorable conditions for the education and social adaptation of children with disabilities. Their integration into society is being pursued primarily through the "General Education Project for Children with Disabilities," which emphasizes the potential of inclusive education. Consequently, in-depth research into the pedagogical and psychological aspects of organizing inclusive education, identifying related issues, and determining its effectiveness has become a pressing scientific challenge.

The inclusive education method creates opportunities for full participation in the learning process for all children, regardless of their mental or physical condition. This approach is especially beneficial for children with special needs, as it allows them to communicate with others, grow to meet the demands of the social environment, acquire daily living skills, adapt to life, study under equal conditions with healthy peers in general education schools, form friendly relationships with them, learn lessons on time, and approach assignments responsibly.

Considering these factors, the task is to substantiate the distinctive indicators of the effectiveness of inclusive education and to identify the necessary pedagogical and psychological approaches for its implementation, starting from the family and preschool institutions through to higher education.

The term "**inclusivity**" is derived from the English word "**inclusive**," meaning to add or integrate. This term refers to the process of teaching students with special needs in general education schools

alongside healthy children. Inclusive education is an educational process that takes into account the students' abilities, individual psychological and physical limitations, and learning characteristics.

In the process of inclusive education, students with special educational needs are taught together with healthy children in the same school and classroom. From the day children with disabilities start school, they require special support, and this support is necessary throughout their entire lives. Therefore, from the early stages of school education, it is essential to create favorable conditions for these students' social development. The educational process involving students with disabilities demands the identification of inclusive education forms and their integration into the general education process. This integration should meet their specific educational needs. If students with disabilities continue their education solely in environments with others like them, it may negatively affect their development and socialization. Being in a uniform environment helps them adapt to the world around them. Teaching methods should be adapted to their abilities, but integrating them with students who have communication difficulties does not provide the necessary conditions for their social development. Children with disabilities need to gain experience in performing the same actions as other students. One of the promising forms of educating students with disabilities is gradually integrating them into groups or classes. This requires them to establish communication with their classmates or group members and account for their learning abilities.

The scope of development among students with disabilities is so broad that it is impossible to create a one-size-fits-all educational process for them. In such cases, many students remain excluded from the educational process. The diversity within the group of students with disabilities shows that the educational process must encompass a variety of conditions. Considering the wide range and complexity of educating students with disabilities, organizing the general secondary education process is necessary. It is important to develop the knowledge, skills, and competencies essential for life in comparison with their normally developing peers within the general education process. In the educational process, knowledge should be presented by considering the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of students with disabilities, creating conditions for them to acquire life skills alongside their peers and relatives.

Inclusive education for children without disabilities implies teaching students with developmental challenges alongside their peers. This approach allows many children in general education schools to open special classes for students who lag behind physically and mentally. To successfully educate such students, well-organized specialized pedagogical and psychological support is required, as well as a significant reduction in the number of students in integrated classes. Inclusive education is also a state policy aimed at eliminating barriers between children with and without disabilities and integrating children in need of inclusive education into the general education system, regardless of their developmental challenges or economic difficulties. This system is focused on adapting them to social life. During childhood, a person is highly influenced both psychologically and pedagogically. The structure and functions of a child's brain develop throughout the growth process. Through corrective-pedagogical work, it is possible to identify and develop a child's unique abilities and potential. Corrective and psychological assistance helps reduce the child's primary disabilities, which in turn helps prevent secondary issues such as low self-esteem, social skills deficits, and learning difficulties. Corrective-pedagogical and psychological approaches help prepare a child for independent living. In this process, it is important to develop the child's self-management, decision-making, and problem-solving skills. Corrective-pedagogical work aids the child in finding their place in society and participating actively in social life. This, in turn, boosts the child's self-confidence and enhances their social skills.

In conclusion, inclusive education is an approach aimed at making the educational process more fair and effective. It ensures that each student's unique characteristics are taken into account and that they actively participate in the educational process. The family's and society's approach, support,

and motivation play a crucial role in the child's development. This approach helps ensure social justice and expands opportunities for every individual.

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